

A STUDY ON A CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS DEPARTMENTAL STORES WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SARAVANAMPATTI AREA IN COIMBATORE CITY.

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ABSTRACT: The intention of this paper is to find out consumer approach towards Departmental stores a shape of organized trade outlet in Saravanampatti in Coimbatore city. A total of 200 consumers of departmental stores were face-to-face surveyed with a structured questionnaire. These consumers are extending out throughout Coimbatore city. Statistical analysis such as Simple percentage analysis and Chi square were carried out. The preferences of the consumers clearly point out their importance of word of mouth is influencing their purchase, the additional amenities expected, improvement expected in handling damaged goods and many. This research analyses the approach of the consumer towards departmental stores. The study was restricted only to Coimbatore city. So the results cannot be comprehensive. The results may help the departmental stores to understand about the factors that influence the approach of consumers towards departmental stores, so that they can implement the requirement of the consumers and be successful in the up-and-coming retailing environment.

Keywords- Customer satisfaction, Departmental store, approach of the customer.

INTRODUCTION:

Business invariably starts and closes with customers and therefore the purchasers should be treated because the King of the market. All the business enhancements, profit, status, image etc of the organization depends on customers. Therefore it's necessary for all the organizations to fulfill all the clients' expectations and establish that they're glad customer. Customer satisfaction is that the live off however the requirements and responses area unit collaborated and delivered to surpass customer expectation. It will solely be earned if the client has associate overall sensible relationship with the provider. In today's competitive business marketplace, customer satisfaction is a vital performance exponent and basic person of business ways. Hence, a lot of customer satisfaction in the business and also the bonding with customers. Customer satisfaction is that the live off but the wants and responses square measure collaborated and delivered to surpass shopper expectation. It'll alone be attained if the shopper has associate overall wise relationship with the supplier. In today's competitive business marketplace, customer satisfaction may be a very important performance exponent and basic person of business ways that. Hence, the plenty of is customer satisfaction; plenty of is that the business and additionally the bonding with shopper. Customer satisfaction is the overall core of the feeling about the supplier by the customers. This feeling which a customer makes regarding supplier is the sum total of all the process he goes through, right from communicating supplier before doing any marketing to post delivery options and services and managing queries or complaints post delivery. During this process the customer comes across working environment of various departments and the type of strategies involved in the association. This helps the customer to make strong opinion about the supplier which finally results in satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

DEPARTMENTAL STORE:

A departmental store may be described as a large retail business having number departmental offers the widest possible range of goods and services at one place. It aims at providing convenience in shopping and can be turned as a "universal provider". A departmental store is a large retailing business unit which handles a wide variety of shopping and specialty goods and is organized into separate department for purposes of promotion, service, and control."-E.1V. Cundiff and K.R. Still

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The study of the customer satisfaction enables us to study one's own decision in shopping. The very look of the departmental store attract people, the way in which products are visited not only to shop, but also spend sometimes and to enjoy the atmosphere, the customer takes a look to choose the product and understands the inferential as well as the external factors. This is done in a clean fresh atmosphere in departmental store. It is an issue for study as to why they prefer departmental store to buy their products.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To study the factor influencing the customer to purchase household articles from the departmental store.

2. To study the customers opinion about the departmental stores.
3. To suggest, improvement and development of the departmental store.

METHODOLOGY:

Collecting data through questionnaire technique was used to collect the data required. Convenient sampling method is adopted under the non-probability sampling technique and about 200 samples have been collected for the study. The questionnaire was planned in such a way that the respondents were able to convey their opinions freely and frankly.

STATISTICAL TOOL FOR ANALYSIS:

- Simple percentage analysis
- Chi –Square

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY:

1. Restricted to Coimbatore city.
2. For convenience , Study made from Kasthuri, AR Departmental store, Vayal Departmental store, and SPAR Departmental store
3. Time limited for two months.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

TABLE 1
TABLE SHOWING THE AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS

Age group of the respondents		
Age	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 20	50	50
21 to 30	75	75
31 to 40	55	55
Above 40	20	20
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 50% of the respondents are below 20 years, 75% of the respondents are between 21 to 30 years, 55% of the respondents are between 31 to 40 years, 20% of the respondents are above 40 years. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 75% of the respondents are shopping in the departmental store falls in the age group of 21 to 30 years.

TABLE 2
TABLE SHOWING THE GENDER OF THE RESPONDENTS

Gender of the respondents		
Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
Male	85	43
Female	115	57
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 43% of the respondents are Male and 57% of the respondents are Female. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 57% of the female respondents are shopping in departmental store.

TABLE 3
TABLE SHOWING THE MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Marital status of the respondents		
Marital Status	No of Respondents	Percentage
Married	155	77
Singles	45	23
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 43% of the respondents are Male and 57% of the respondents are Female. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 57% of the female respondents are shopping in departmental store.

TABLE 4
TABLE SHOWING THE QUALIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Qualification of the respondents		
Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage
School	30	15
Graduate	70	35
Post Graduate	50	25
Professional	50	25
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 15% of the respondents are school level, 35% of the respondents are graduate person, 25% of the respondents are post graduate person, and 25% of the respondents are professionals. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 35% of the graduate respondents are shopping in departmental stores

TABLE 5
TABLE SHOWING THE OCCUPATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Occupation of the respondents		
Occupation	No of Respondents	Percentage
Students	23	12
Housewife	70	35
Salaried people	57	28
Business person	50	25
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 12% of the respondents are students, 35% of the respondents are housewife, 28% of the respondents are salaried people, and 25% of the respondents are business person. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 35% of the housewife respondents are shopping in departmental stores

TABLE 6
TABLE SHOWING THE INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS

Income of the respondents		
Income	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 10,000	40	20
10,000 to 20,000	50	25
20,001 to 30,000	70	35
Above 30,000	40	20
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 20% of the respondents are below 10,000, 25% of the respondents are 10,000 to 20,000, 35% of the respondents are 20,001 to 30,000, and 20% of the respondents are above 30,000. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 35% of the income respondents are shopping in departmental stores

TABLE 7
TABLE SHOWING THE FAMILY SIZE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Family size of the respondents		
Size	No of Respondents	Percentage
Up to 2	20	10
3 to 4	110	55
5 to 6	60	30
Above 6	10	5
Total	200	100

INTERPRETATION:

The above table shows that 10% of the respondents are up to 2, 55% of the respondents are 3 to 4, 30% of the respondents are 5 to 6, and 5% of the respondents are above 6. Thus the table reveals the fact that majority 55% of the 3 to 4 family size respondents are shopping in departmental stores.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AGE AND THE LEVEL OF SATISFACTION.**HYPOTHESIS:**

H₀ : There is no significant relationship between age and the level of satisfaction.

H₁: There is significant relationship between age and the level of satisfaction.

Results				
Age	High	Moderate	Low	Totals
below 20	10 (11.25) [0.14]	30 (28.75) [0.05]	10 (10.00) [0.00]	50
21 to 30	20 (16.88) [0.58]	40 (43.12) [0.23]	15 (15.00) [0.00]	75
31 to 40	10 (12.38) [0.46]	35 (31.62) [0.36]	10 (11.00) [0.09]	55
above 40	5 (4.50) [0.06]	10 (11.50) [0.20]	5 (4.00) [0.25]	20
Totals	45	115	40	200 (Grand Total)

INTERPRETATION:

The chi-square statistic is 2.4065. The p-value is 0.878782. The result is not significant at $p < 0.05$. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction.

CHI SQUARE ANALYSIS ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GENDER AND LEVEL OF SATISFACTION**HYPOTHESIS:**

H₀: There is no significant relationship between gender and level of satisfaction.

H₁: There is significant relationship between gender and level of satisfaction.

Results				
Gender	High	Moderate	Low	Totals
male	20 (21.25) [0.07]	55 (51.00) [0.31]	10 (12.75) [0.59]	85
female	30 (28.75) [0.05]	65 (69.00) [0.23]	20 (17.25) [0.44]	115
Totals	50	120	30	200 (Grand Total)

INTERPRETATION:

The chi-square statistic is 1.705. The p-value is 0.426341. The result is not significant at $p < 0.05$. Therefore, null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant relationship between gender and level of satisfaction.

FINDINGS:

- Majority 75% of the respondents are shopping in the departmental store falls in the age group of 21 to 30 years.
- Majority 57% of the female respondents are shopping in departmental store.
- Majority 57% of the female respondents are shopping in departmental store.
- Majority 35% of the graduate respondents are shopping in departmental stores
- Majority 35% of the housewife respondents are shopping in departmental stores
- Majority 35% of the income respondents are shopping in departmental stores
- Majority 55% of the 3 to 4 family size respondents are shopping in departmental stores.
- Null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant relationship between age and level of satisfaction.
- Null hypothesis is accepted and there is no significant relationship between gender and level of satisfaction.

SUGGESTIONS:

- Majority of the respondent are aware of departmental store not through advertisement, it is suggest that need little more effort on advertising and showcase of their store.
- If the department store recruits more staff and help the customer to easily found the products.
- Parking facility is little more to develop so it may attract more customers.
- Billing process is little slow so need to be improved in that process.
- Department store should make awareness about the door delivery and the offers price properly.

CONCLUSION:

Customer satisfaction plays an important role in departmental store. The departmental store is where we get all items in a single retail shop. So if the customers are satisfied only they will have the intention to come again. The departmental store should keep up neatness and arrange the items properly and attract the customers. The study reveals that customers are satisfied with the departmental store and ready to recommend to other customers.

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